

Paper 2**A STUDY ON VARIOUS STRESSORS THAT CAUSE STRESS AMONG CABIN CREWS, PROPOSED STRESS MODEL AND RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS****Pavithra Kumari**

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ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4541-4242>, E-mail: pavithrakumarishetty@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

The study's goal is to learn more about the numerous stressors that create stress among cabin crew workers. A model is established to comprehend this, and a research hypothesis is created based on this model. The research hypothesis assists in the resolution of the study issue. It explains in great detail what the research will entail. The translation of the research questions into a forecast is the initial step in every investigation. Variables, population, and their relationships are all included. A simple hypothesis is used to evaluate the relationship between the variables in this study. The model below depicts the many stressor factors that create stress in cabin workers, as well as their reactions. The hypothesis is illustrated below using this model.

Keywords: Stressor Agents, Hypothesis, Variables, Cabin Crews,

1. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The success of the research study depends critically on the research premise. The research method cannot be fully understood without the research hypothesis, and the conclusions would be constrained in their applicability. The research idea comes before the research hypothesis. The development of a research hypothesis enables a more precise characterization of the statistical approach to be taken into account for the investigation at hand [1-3]. In the context of the entire project, a strong research hypothesis aids in the clarification of the specifics of the statistical evaluation. The research project is constructed around the research hypothesis. In this regard, the research hypothesis is crucial to the protocol's overall success. The successful execution of a suitable protocol will be ensured by having a well-planned hypothesis [4].

2. STRESS IN AVIATION SECTOR

The aviation industry is a well-known example of contemporary tourism. The efficiency of the aviation sector is highly dependent on the quality of customer service provided. Aviation customer services is responsible for a wide range of tasks, including checking in passengers, providing support in the VIP lounge, assisting passengers in need of travel information at the counters, managing the flight control centre, managing luggage and load control, and a host of other tasks. Airports and airfields serve as the primary locations for employees who engage in aviation customer service. According to various studies, there is a link between rising stress and the work of customer care representatives in the aviation industry. The increase in crew stress levels has resulted in a large increase in staff turnover, poor job performance, and the adoption of potentially hazardous work behaviours [5-8]. It should be noted that the amount of evidence

available to explain why there is such a high level of pressure among aeroplane customer service workers is insufficient; therefore, additional research should be carried out.

3. CABIN CREWS

Cabin Crew members are on board an aircraft to ensure passenger safety and comfort. Even if no food or drink is provided, a minimum cabin crew presence is required for safety reasons in the UK. Cabin crew members must give exceptional customer service while remaining cheery, approachable, and enthusiastic at all times, as well as maintaining a professional look, because they represent the airline's public image. Cabin crew work can be physically hard, and you must be willing to work on any given day of the year, regardless of the weather. On the other side, this presents you with a fantastic opportunity to break out from the monotony of a regular 9-to-5 job. Cabin crew may encounter a range of situations when operating on board an aircraft. In order to succeed, they must be strong team players who can also operate independently, utilising quick thinking and organisational skills. The main responsibility of the Cabin Crew includes all pre-departure services between the time of boarding and the moment of take-off. [9-12]

4. THE CONSEQUENCES OF STRESS ON HELATH AND WELL BEING

Stress can have a positive or negative impact on humans, having implications for both psychological and physiological well-being. In many cases, stress is misunderstood as a type of adaptive response. In the absence of stress, the body may become overly quiet and inactive, making it difficult to cope with stressful situations. Stress has an effect on the nervous system, which responds in a manner that is comparable to how the body responds to stress. It has been discovered that the level of epinephrine [an adrenaline derivative] in the blood has increased. Among the many biological responses induced by this hormone include increased metabolic rate, stimulation of heart motions, and rise of blood pressure, among others. It is a powerful stimulant that supports the body in responding to specific conditions and dealing with stressful circumstances. As a result, most people experience a sense of terror as a result of this. The ability to respond to a situation successfully is impaired in those who are panicked [13- 16].

5. STRESS MODEL

The conceptual framework for the study is presented in the figure 1.1. In this model the independent variables are the long Irregular working hours, Work Engagement, Work Hassles, Aircraft Cabin Environment, Social Isolation and Emotional Labour. And the dependent variable is Psychological and Physiological Stress. This paradigm distinguishes between demanding workplace conditions and personal pressures. Strains can be mental, physical, or emotional, and they frequently differ from person to person.

6. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

The researcher reviewed a few earlier works by scholars in order to formulate study questions and offer a predicted outcome. The investigations were based on stressor agents and were relevant to the researcher's current research. The link between the variables is studied in this work using a basic hypothesis based on the above stress model. The following model depicts the many stressor agents that lead cabin staff to become stressed, as well as their reactions. The following is a description of the research hypothesis.

(a) Irregular working hours and fatigue: Authors Marta Castroa, Jose Carvalhaisb and Julia Telesc [17], in their study ‘Irregular working hours and fatigue of cabin crew’ focus on the trigger of fatigue symptoms due to irregular schedules in a wet lease Portuguese airline. 73 cabin crew members [39 females and 34 males] were given a questionnaire to study this factor. The study clearly points out the presence of fatigue and corresponding health symptoms among the airlines cabin crew. work and environment-related factors both contributed to the fatigue among the cabin crew. The study also shows that senior cabin crews were significantly more affected by lack of humidity in the cabin. They also more affected by sleep and stomach problem. Women are also more affected by a variety of fatigue factors than males, and they report more complaints about body discomfort and other fatigue symptoms. Despite the flight attendant duty and rest restrictions, some airlines are starting to use the minimal rest period for crew members. Because the minimum rest duration does not correspond to the effective rest period, this condition may result in less sleep [only four to six hours]

Approximately half of the people questioned said they become exhausted at the end of flights frequently or usually, while 40.6 percent say it happens occasionally. The three main elements contributing to exhaustion, according to the flight attendant, were the medium or longhaul trip, the lack of humidity, and temperature oscillations in the cabin. In the same way, regarding other work-related factors contributing to fatigue, the night flights [45.2%], the jet lag [43.9%], the scheduling irregularity [41.1%] and the lack of rest [35.6%] were the most referred ones. Similarly, when it came to other work-related problems that contribute to fatigue, night flights [45.2%], jet lag [43.9%], scheduling inconsistency [41.1%], and a lack of sleep [35.6%] were the most commonly mentioned. So based on this study and the findings in support to the relationship between irregular working hours and fatigue following hypothesis is framed:

H1.1: The longer the flight hours the greater the amount of fatigue felt by the airline cabin crews.

H1.2: The lesser the humidity in the cabin the greater is its affect among the cabin crews.

H1.3: The lesser is the rest duration the greater is the body discomfort and fatigue felt by the cabin crews.

H1.4: The longer the flight hours the greater the amount of jet lag among cabin crews.

H1.5: The more the number of night flights the greater is the fatigue felt by the cabin crews.

(b) Burnout and Work Engagement Among Cabin Crew: In this study the authors applied the job demands-resources model to study burnout and work engagement among cabin crew. A sample of 305 Taiwanese flight attendants were used to study the experiences and consequences of work demand [18]. Flight attendants have more responsibility than other front-line service sector professionals. This is because, they are trained first to manage cabin safety and then to provide customer service on board. They are people who have a tight work schedule and frequently suffer from physical ailments and mental tiredness as a result of jet lag and a constantly changing work schedule. They are frequently unable to manage daily family and social lives for long periods of time due to their shift-work schedule. Work-family issues result in increased work-related stress, which leads to burnout among flight attendants. Work - Family conflict, Possibility for development and social support, Burnout, Work engagement, Health problems and Turnover intention these measures was constructed for participants to respond to with regard to the flight attendant job conditions The health issues induced by severe workloads in specific working conditions, as well as significant rates of turnover intention, were noted in the study. The results show that job demands are positively related to burnout when using structural equation modelling to test the conceptual model. Furthermore, health issues cause turnover intention and act as a mediator between burnout and turnover intention. Based on the above study, and relation between job demand and burnout following hypothesis is framed

H2.1: Job demands are positively related to burnout.

H2.2: Burnout is positively related to health problems.

H2.3: Burnout is positively related to turnover intention.

H2.4: Health problems are positively related to turnover intention.

H2.5: Work - family issues result in increased work-related stress.

(c) Work Hassles of Cabin Crew: In a study “Hassles of cabin crew [19]: An exploratory study” by Sheng-Hshiang Tsaur, Fu-Sung Hsu and Li-Hua Kung, they tried to explore the hassles of cabin crew by using the content analysis method. Purposive sampling and snowball sampling were adopted for participant selection. Researchers invited participants to interviews based on suggestions from other participants through the researcher's personal working network. A total of 16 Taiwanese flight attendants were interviewed. This study investigated the problem of flight attendants. As part of a qualitative study, 16 Taiwanese flight attendants were interviewed. Through careful content analysis, authors have compiled four themes of cabin crew hassles that address 13 types of anxieties. The four types of hassles are; 1. Job hassle 2. Peer interaction hassle 3. Passenger service hassle and 4. Personal hassles. Work problems arise from gaps between work standards and actual operations, inadequate service capacity of aircraft facilities, irregular work schedules and emergencies. Difficulties in interacting with colleagues include uneven work allocations between flight attendants, inadequate work chunks between flight attendants, and inadequate work chunks between cockpits and flight attendants. Passenger service issues arise from oral and physical violence against crew members, sexual harassment of crew members, theft during night flights, and passengers hiding infections. Personal issues include family and work conflicts and physical health issues. Going through the papers on work hassles of Cabin Crew following hypothesis is derived

H3.1: Gap between work standards and practical operations are positively related to work stress

H3.2: Poor peer interaction and poor work cohesion between cockpit crew and cabin crew are positively related to cabin crew stress

H3.3: expected/ unexpected turbulences of different intensity during the flight positively related to stress of cabin crew

H3.4: Violent behaviours and misconducts of passengers towards cabin crew are positively related to cabin crew stress

H3.5: Work-family conflicts are positively related to cabin crew stress

(d) Emotional labour and emotional exhaustion of Cabin Crews: Emotional labour is the act of controlling one's emotions in order to meet organisational standards [20]. studies have looked at the two variables of emotional labour and emotional exhaustion, and even fewer have looked at flight attendants as a research subject. This study used a questionnaire to examine the feelings of 353 Taiwanese flight attendants about emotional labour, the status of their emotional exhaustion, and the relationship between emotional labour and emotional exhaustion. The study's findings show that: 1] while female flight attendants' emotional labour is medium to high, their perception of emotional exhaustion is only medium; 2] female flight attendants' emotional labour has a significant positive correlation with their emotional exhaustion; and 3] among the perspectives of emotional labour, the qualities of "deep emotional masking" and "multiformity" have a significant predictive effect. Another study is being conducted to investigate the impact of emotional labour and its two forms – deep acting and surface acting – on the overall health of airline employees [21]. Surface acting entails feigning the desired feelings: those who engage in surface acting do not truly strive to experience the emotions they seek to portray. They may put on "false smiles" or other emotionally demanded displays that may not reflect their genuine feelings. Deep acting, on the other hand, entails genuinely feeling and expressing the required emotions. When deep acting, people try to change their feelings to fit the appropriate display criteria. Furthermore, the study seeks to determine whether emotional labour and its two forms, deep acting and surface acting, have any effect across demographics. Gender, age, marital status, and work tenure are among the demographics examined in the study. A quantitative research design is used in this study. Employees of airlines are given survey forms. This study enlisted the help of 295 airline employees. Among the 295 participants, 190 are cabin crew and 105 are airline ground personnel. According to the findings of the study, emotional labour has no significant impact on the overall health of airline employees. Furthermore, neither deep nor surface acting has a significant impact on the overall health of employees. According to the findings, emotional labour-deep and surface acting differ across demographics. Female employees are subjected to more emotional labour than male employees. Female employees also engage in more intense acting than their male counterparts. Employees between the ages of 31 and 35, with 11 to 15 years of experience, are observed to be subjected to more emotional labour than their counterparts. This study has significant implications for HRM departments in industries as well as Aviation Psychology in India. By going through these studies, it is hypothesised that;

H4.1: Female flight attendants' emotional labour has a significant positive correlation with the stress

H4.2: Deep emotional acting has a positive relation with the stress of cabin crews than the surface acting

H4.3: Female cabin crews are subjected to more emotional labour than male employees

H4.4: Age and experience factors are positively related to more emotional labour than their counterparts.

H4.5: Emotional labour has no significant impact on the overall health of cabin crews working environment of every airline is different and the environment of every aircraft of the same airline could be different.

(e) Aircraft cabin Environments: This study looked into the effects of flying on Indian male and female flight attendants [FAs] who had been flying for more than 10 years and up to 30 years [22]. The flight attendants chosen for this study were all subjected to the identical set of constraints, such as monthly flight hours and flight itineraries. Questionnaires were created based on complaints received on a regular basis as well as interviews with a limited group of flight attendants. In addition, the researchers spoke with 130 flight attendants, either before or after their departure, and obtained full surveys from them while ensuring anonymity. As a result, 88.85 percent of flight attendants have stated that they are stressed "frequently" or "often." Many participants believed that if their workplace was more employee-friendly, their stress levels would decrease. Back pain was noted by 72.65% of flight attendants, who claimed that it might be alleviated in major part by better equipment and user-friendly galleys. Memory loss was found in 67.47 percent of FAs tested. Headaches affect 58.42 percent of flight attendants. Hypoxia, jetlag, and inconsistent sleep appear to be common causes of stress, memory loss, and headaches. Hearing loss, which affected 51.37 percent of flight attendants, was not a major source of concern but was viewed as an inconvenience. Finally, experts concluded that flight attendants' occupational health issues require quick and significant treatment.

H5.1: Reduced cabin pressure and, consequently, reduced oxygen availability, positively contribute to headaches, nausea and respiratory effects.

H5.2: Many exposures related to aircraft cabin environments causes health problems among cabin crews

H5.3: Irregular and inadequate sleep among cabin crews is positively related to undesirable effects on the health among them.

H5.4: The aircraft cabin environment is positively at risk of transmitting potentially serious airborne diseases and it results in stress among cabin crew

H5.5: longer flights, longer aisles and more amenities to offer passengers increases the workload of flight attendants which may result in cabin crew stress.

(f) Social Isolation: The study is a first look at the psychological stress levels and sources of work-related stress among aircrew personnel [23]. The research also looks at how aircrew members deal with stress and analyses the findings based on a variety of characteristics. A total of 226 aircrew men were included in the study. To improve this study, two scales were used: causes of work stress and skills for dealing with psychological stress. Face validity, construction validity, differential validity, and the coefficient Cronbach – Alpha Test were used to produce these scales, which were shown to be trustworthy for the purposes of this study. According to the findings, aircrew members' perceptions of job stress were medium [74.33 percent], work produced high pressure [11.50 percent], and they did not feel any work-related stresses [14.15 percent]. Surprisingly, males experience work-related stress more frequently than females, and less experienced aircrew members report higher levels of stress. The most widely used strategies

of coping with psychological stress, according to the study, are cognitive skills, interpersonal skills, and personal skills, in that order; however, that the degree of usage of these skills was below average, and avoiding skills was the least used. Finally, prolonged absence and lack of communication with family and other members of the community may result in a loss of support from parents, spouses, friends, and the community, which alleviates the impacts of social stress on them. This is in line with research that show that working as an airline pilot induces stress. Based on the study the following hypothesis is derived

H6.1: Lack of communication with the family members for a long time is positively related to cause stress among the cabin crews

H6.2: Lack of support from parents, friends and spouses results in stress among cabin crews

H6.3: Cabin attendants experience stress when they are separated from their spouses for an extended period of time.

H6.4: Cabin crews become emotionally exhausted when they are separated from their pals and are unable to express their feelings.

H6.5: Lack of Social participation and lack of communication with the community members is positively related to stress

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